

DivAirCity: Developing digital tools for Citizen Engagement and Climate Neutral Cities

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Abstract—The rapid urbanization and challenges related to climate change challenges demand innovative technological solutions to achieve climate-neutral cities. Innovative technologies, however, can tackle the lack of awareness among citizens, enhancing their participation in a sustainable urban transformation process. The DivAirCity project promotes Nature Based Solutions (NBS) to improve air quality and decarbonization in EU cities. It has also developed an application, which incorporates a hybrid platform, designed to promote citizen engagement. As a core element of the DivAirCity project, this application motivates citizens participation, by tracking their routes and modes of transport, incentivizing eco-friendly behavior, through a blockchain-based tokenization approach and a traditional backend system. The application is not limited only to the above functionalities but acts as an enabler to behavioural change in the city, promoting diversity, inclusion and sustainable urban mobility. The scope of this paper is to present the different functionalities of the DivAirCity application, as well as its overall structure combining a framework for blockchain and cloud services. The DivAirCity app can also serve as an educational tool, encouraging eco-friendly behaviors and informing citizens on hybrid systems' practical use. Moreover, its citizen-generated environmental data could be exploited by universities for research on urban sustainability. Students can also benefit, since the app can be utilized as an interactive platform to get a deeper insight in decentralized technologies, through hands-on engagement.

Keywords—*climate-neutral cities, blockchain-based incentivization, citizen engagement, sustainable urban mobility, air quality monitoring*

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid pace of urbanization and climate change has intensified environmental challenges, particularly in cities, where air pollution, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and -sometimes- inefficient transportation systems contribute to sustainability concerns [1]. Addressing these issues requires innovative technological solutions that not only mitigate environmental impact but also encourage citizen engagement in shaping climate-neutral cities. Even though traditional policies and urban planning efforts drive sustainable practices [2], digital tools and decentralized technologies can offer new opportunities to promote eco-friendly behaviors and achieve active public participation in environmental monitoring and improvement.

The DivAirCity project responds to these challenges, targeting diverse citizens' groups, by integrating blockchain and cloud infrastructure in a single application, in order to promote sustainable mobility, air quality monitoring and behavioral change. Through a token-based incentivization system, the application encourages users to adopt greener

transportation choices, contribute real-time environmental data, and participate in a reward-based ecosystem. This hybrid approach enhances urban sustainability efforts while ensuring transparency, data integrity and user engagement.

In this paper we present the DivAirCity application, detailing its system architecture, core functionalities and impact on public awareness and behavioral change. Additionally, we explore the app's role as an educational tool and research resource, leveraging citizen-generated data to support academic studies and urban policy development. Lastly, the paper discusses potential enhancements, including AI-driven environmental forecasting, adaptive incentives and automated transport mode detection, to further optimize the app's effectiveness.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

Blockchain is a distributed ledger technology that enables secure, transparent, and tamper-resistant transactions across a decentralized network. Unlike traditional centralized systems, blockchain records data in an immutable chain of blocks, where each block contains a cryptographic hash of the previous one, ensuring security and integrity. This technology is already widely utilized in finance, supply chain management and digital identity verification sustainability efforts. By eliminating intermediaries, blockchain fosters efficiency, traceability and trust, making it a powerful tool for industries seeking secure data sharing, automated transactions via smart contracts and decentralized governance [3].

Integrating Blockchain technology in sustainability efforts has gained significant traction in recent years, due to the fact that it provides alternative solutions to environmental challenges. In line with the DivAirCity initiative, which - as already mentioned- leverages blockchain-based tokenization to endorse eco-friendly behavior and track air quality, various existing projects demonstrate the feasibility along with the impact of decentralized systems in addressing sustainability and carbon footprint reduction, while properly incentivizing the user. Some of these projects' valuable insights are presented as follows, in order to further demonstrate blockchain's potential for enhancing transparency, incentivization and decentralized environmental governance.

One notable example is IBM's Plastic Bank, which operates on a blockchain-based banking platform running on IBM Cloud. More analytically, its concept is built around the idea that plastic waste could function as an exchange medium. In other words, participants collect plastic and exchange it for rewards stored in an online account. Afterwards, the collected plastic is sold to major brands that recycle materials into their products. Additionally, the platform integrates incentives, group rewards, user ratings and gamification elements to favor

continued participation [4]. Similarly, PTwist explores blockchain-based gamification techniques to increase citizen participation in plastic recycling. In fact, the project combines crowdsourcing tools, digital wallets, a reward system and a virtual marketplace. Hence, it raises the interest on circular economy practices and trusted collaboration among citizens, grassroots groups and stakeholders. The platform is tested through three pilot programs, to ensure its practical application [5].

Blockchain has not been implemented only for waste management, but also to improve air quality monitoring and to assist in carbon footprint reduction. PlanetWatch [6], for instance, leverages blockchain to motivate individuals and organizations to deploy air quality sensors, creating a decentralized, immutable database of environmental data. The project aims to establish a global network of high-density, low-cost sensors that are small, quiet and unobtrusive. These sensors are made available to citizens who use them and transfer the air quality data to the blockchain ledger. In return for their participation, users are rewarded with tokens, strengthening user's engagement in air quality monitoring.

Another initiative, Climatetrade [7], employs blockchain to facilitate carbon credit transactions, allowing businesses and individuals to offset their emissions transparently and efficiently. The platform operates as a marketplace, designed to streamline carbon offsetting by eliminating intermediaries, supporting companies' direct investments in environmental projects. Through blockchain, it guarantees full traceability of transactions, offering to users control over their carbon offset decisions. When a purchase is initiated, the exact carbon footprint of a product or service is calculated, and users can choose which sustainability projects to support. Upon completion, they receive a digital certificate detailing the offset transaction. The platform has been adopted by several companies and institutions in Spain as part of real-world case studies.

Moreover, the energy sector has increasingly assimilated blockchain technology to facilitate decentralized energy exchange and promote renewable energy adoption.

In this context, [8] has developed an ecosystem of applications, which emphasized on decentralized energy exchange, grid balancing distributed applications (dApps), electric vehicle charging dApps and retailer billing dApps. One notable application is the decentralized retailer model, which utilizes a virtual machine acting as an autonomous agent on a blockchain to facilitate trustless, peer-to-peer energy transactions. A complementary initiative, "Rooftop that Feeds" project by Comunitaria [9] utilizes solar energy generated in poor neighborhoods to provide access to food at local shops. Smart Building IoT hubs monitor the produced solar energy, while a blockchain-based application facilitates transactions. In this system, residents sell the solar energy they generate to local businesses, which, in turn, pay using a Community Currency -an ERC-20 sidechain token. This digital currency is then either used by residents to purchase goods from participating local shops or donated to support vulnerable families.

Collectively, these projects illustrate blockchain's transformative potential in sustainability, urban mobility and environmental monitoring. By drawing on analogous decentralized mechanisms for incentivization, data integrity and community engagement, DivAirCity creates a hybrid

platform that cultivates climate-conscious behavior, whereas it incorporates blockchain into the broader smart city ecosystem.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Throughout its lifecycle, the DivAirCity app has evolved into a cross-platform hybrid decentralized application designed to combine the transparency and immutability of blockchain technology with the flexibility of traditional backend systems (Fig. 1). It leverages the Alastria [8] Red-B blockchain network to manage decentralized logic and secure operations, such as smart contract execution and tamper-proof record-keeping. At the same time, it integrates with a FastAPI [9] backend to handle off-chain operations that require efficiency and privacy.

Fig. 1. System Architecture

A. Blockchain

The Alastria Red-B Blockchain acts as the foundation for DivAirCity's decentralized architecture. As a permissioned blockchain network within the Alastria ecosystem, Alastria Red-B is built using Hyperledger Besu, an enterprise-grade Ethereum client tailored for regulated environments. It facilitates private transactions, smart contract deployment and interoperability with Ethereum-based applications. Leveraging the IBFT 2.0 consensus mechanism, it ensures rapid and secure transaction finality while promoting transparency and accountability among consortium members. Through a collaborative partnership with Alastria, a dedicated node has been established to support the application's operations.

This node enables the deployment of smart contracts that underpin the application's decentralized logic across each city, with users securely interacting through its RPC endpoint. These smart contracts manage all core functionalities, including token transactions, live tracking, areas and routes of interest, the marketplace and donation mechanisms.

B. Backend and Cloud Infrastructure

Complementing the blockchain layer is the FastAPI backend, paired with a MongoDB database, which together facilitate optional, more centralized services for tasks that are less suited to the blockchain implementation. FastAPI is a modern, high-performance web framework for building APIs in Python, offering automatic request validation, interactive API documentation and support for asynchronous operations.

MongoDB [12], a NoSQL database, is renowned for its flexibility and scalability. It stores data in BSON (a binary JSON format), enabling dynamic, schema-less data structures. MongoDB's features include horizontal scaling through sharding, advanced querying capabilities and real-time data change tracking with change streams. Together, these systems form the traditional backend of the DivAirCity application, creating a robust stack for implementing key features such as air-quality data collection and enhanced user experiences.

The Cloud Infrastructure supports air-quality data collection, allowing users to contribute environmental insights and earn additional token rewards. Furthermore, it enhances the user experience with features like the friends list, which records public addresses of other users for token transfers. The traditional backend also supports potential future features requested by cities, such as certificates or access codes for public solar chargers. While these additions provide enhanced functionality and convenience, they remain non-essential to the core operation of the application.

C. App – User Interface

The DivAirCity application is developed using Flutter [13], an open-source framework created by Google for building cross-platform applications. Flutter enables the development of natively compiled applications for mobile (iOS and Android), web and desktop from a single codebase. Its popularity stems from its high performance, customizable UI components and streamlined development process, making it an ideal choice for creating responsive and visually rich applications across multiple platforms.

D. Analytics and Visualization

The DivAirCity application is connected to an InfluxDB [14] database that tracks analytic data related to system operations. InfluxDB is an open-source, high-performance time-series database designed to manage large volumes of time-stamped data. It is optimized for the storage, querying and visualization of time-series data, making it ideal for applications involving metrics, monitoring and sensor data. In addition, it integrates seamlessly with various tools and platforms, including Grafana for advanced data visualization.

Grafana [15], an open-source platform for monitoring, visualization and alerting on metrics and logs, provides powerful tools for building interactive dashboards and supports integration with numerous data sources. Within the DivAirCity application, Grafana queries the InfluxDB database to produce visual representations of user interaction analytics.

The task execution service handles the automated execution of user-reward blockchain transactions, performing this operation once daily for each city's smart contract. Concurrently, the event listening service monitors events generated by the deployed smart contracts, capturing and storing their anonymized payloads in a database for further analysis.

IV. APPLICATION

This section presents the DivAirCity mobile-web application (Fig. 2), detailing its core features and functionalities. It emphasizes how the application facilitates eco-friendly behaviors through user engagement and reward mechanisms while safeguarding user privacy.

Fig. 2. DivAirCity Mobile Application

A. Core Functionalities

The application defines three distinct user roles -Citizen, Vendor and Municipality- each with tailored access rights to the app, based on their respective responsibilities within the ecosystem. The Citizen role, which is the default for all new users, is the most commonly assigned. Vendors, a specialized subset of Citizens, have extended access privileges that enable them to manage item redemptions. Municipality users, in contrast, hold a unique administrative role, responsible for overseeing and managing city-wide operations.

The Municipality user is responsible for administering the content of each city. Their authorized activities include managing available transportation modes, defining areas and routes of interest and adding products and services to the marketplace. To facilitate these tasks, only this user type has access to a web-based version of the application, providing a user-friendly interface for efficient city content management.

The Vendor user has access to all the functionalities available to Citizen users, with additional capabilities to view their listed products and redeem items. In collaboration with the Municipality, Vendors can add their products or services to the marketplace for users to purchase. These items can then be redeemed at the Vendor's physical stores or designated locations.

The Citizen user, the default role for anyone accessing the app, serves as the primary role with the most comprehensive functionality. Their key activities include tracing routes within their city and uploading them to earn tokens. These tokens can then be exchanged for products in the marketplace and redeemed at participating shops.

A key feature of the DivAirCity application is its real-time route-tracking functionality. Leveraging GPS technology, the application captures data, such as distance traveled, time spent in eco-friendly areas (e.g. parks and green spaces) and associated environmental impact metrics. Users can also perform route tracking using a mobile air quality sensor, allowing them to earn additional tokens while contributing to broader environmental analysis. Citizen users can track their progress, review historical routes, and gain insights into their activities while being incentivized to adopt greener transportation methods through rewards determined by the eco-friendliness of their routes.

The built-in token wallet enables users to manage blockchain-based rewards earned through their eco-friendly

activities. Users can view token balances, send tokens to other users and redeem tokens in the marketplace for goods or services. This feature is seamlessly integrated with the app's blockchain infrastructure to ensure transparent, verifiable transactions.

The marketplace offers a range of items that users can access using their earned tokens. Citizens may also choose to donate tokens to environmental initiatives or community projects. Besides, a cloud account can grant users access to extra resources and services that support both sustainable practices and educational opportunities. This feature encourages users to adopt eco-friendly behaviors by providing tangible rewards that align with sustainable practices.

B. Incentive and Privacy Considerations

The DivAirCity application leverages a blockchain-based reward system to promote sustainable behavior among users while ensuring that privacy considerations are embedded within the system's design. This subsection details how the incentive structure motivates eco-friendly activities and the measures taken to safeguard user privacy.

The blockchain-powered reward mechanism is central to motivating user participation. DivAirCity uses smart contracts deployed on the Alastria Red-B blockchain network to automate the distribution of tokens based on predefined eco-friendly behaviors. Users earn tokens by carrying out activities such as walking, cycling or using public transportation, all tracked via the app's route-tracking feature. This decentralized approach ensures transparency and trust, as token distribution is fully auditable and immutable.

It should be always kept in mind that DivAirCity's token ecosystem is designed to be versatile and user-centric. Thus it is completely up to users how they will manage their earned tokens. For instance, they could either redeem them in the marketplace for goods and services, donate them to environmental initiatives or to community projects or send them to a friend.

Given the sensitive nature of user data, privacy has been a core focus in the development of DivAirCity application architecture. The application adheres to a principle of data minimization, collecting only the essential information required for functionality. Route data and user actions are anonymized and aggregated, where possible, to reduce exposure to personally identifiable information. While blockchain transactions are inherently transparent, the DivAirCity app ensures that users' identities remain private, even as their transactions are visible on the blockchain. Sensitive user information is stored in the backend's MongoDB database, where robust encryption is applied both in transit and at rest. Users are empowered to manage their own data through the app's privacy settings. They can modify or delete account information as needed and have full transparency regarding how their data is collected, stored and used. Clear consent mechanisms are provided for all data-related actions.

DivAirCity adheres to relevant data protection regulations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), to ensure users' privacy rights are upheld. This compliance guarantees that users have control over their data and that the system operates in a legally sound manner. By balancing incentive mechanisms with stringent privacy protections, DivAirCity aims to build a trusted platform that motivates

users to adopt eco-friendly behaviors while respecting their data privacy.

V. EVALUATION AND DISCUSSION

The effectiveness of the DivAirCity application in fostering public awareness and behavioral change, the app's role as an educational tool and research resource, and finally, some potential enhancements that could further improve the system are examined next.

A. Public Awareness and Behavioral Change

The DivAirCity application is currently being tested across five pilot cities, Bucharest - Romania, Aarhus - Denmark, Orvieto - Italy, Potsdam - Germany and Castellón - Spain, with the aim of upholding public awareness and behavioral change through blockchain-based incentivization. By engaging citizens in eco-friendly transportation choices and air quality monitoring, the app promotes a data-driven approach to urban sustainability while rewarding environmentally responsible behavior.

Across these cities, the app users -i.e. citizens belonging to different social groups like daily commuters, students or elderly- have been equipped with portable air quality sensors (currently 5 in total), which they can attach to their bicycles, backpacks or vehicles etc. These sensors continuously monitor parameters such as particulate matter (PM₁, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀), temperature, humidity, and atmospheric pressure. As soon as the users activate their sensors, they are able to continuously record air pollution levels along their route and feed real-time environmental data into the DivAirCity system via the DivAirCity app.

Additionally, the app enhances user engagement by enabling direct connections between citizens, allowing them to add friends using nicknames rather than manually entering or scanning public addresses each time they want to send or exchange tokens. This feature strengthens social interaction within the platform, making the peer-to-peer token ecosystem more accessible and user-friendly. However, friends list is not the only feature engaging users to the DivAirCity system, as users' capabilities in marketplace and donations platform play also an important role. More explicitly, users are also able to redeem their tokens in the marketplace for eco-friendly products, services and discounts, or donate them to environmental initiatives and community-driven projects. These social features encourage ongoing participation, promote collective action and enhance the overall user experience.

The application is currently in its testing phase and has not yet been deployed for widespread use. Despite this, it has received strong acceptance among participating citizens across different social groups. From December 2024 to April 2025, a total of 127 users actively engaged with the platform as testers. Collectively, these users covered over 400 kilometers across all participating cities, contributing valuable mobility and air quality data. Furthermore, the application facilitated 98 total visits to predefined Areas or Routes of Interest, demonstrating its potential to guide user behavior and support targeted environmental monitoring.

A Federated Data System has also been implemented within the DivAirCity project, enabling continuous monitoring of the application while providing access to key statistics and performance indicators in real time, especially as the app gains more traction.

The early findings from the implementation of the DivAirCity app in the five pilot cities suggest a growing trend in behavioral adaptation towards sustainability. An increased number of citizens use the proposed green routes or visit the areas of interest. Also a trend appears to replace car transports with cycling or walking leading eventually to a measurable decrease in urban emissions. Moreover, local city administrations have begun to get more familiarized with setting areas and routes of interest and handling the marketplace and donations ecosystems. Two of the most prominent DivAirCity pilot implementations are those in Aarhus and Orvieto, which further illustrate the platform's potential in driving behavioral change and public awareness.

More specifically, in Aarhus, the focus has been on "clean air routes" intervention, where the app encourages users to pass along low-emission pathways, helping them make informed decisions about their daily commutes and encouraging the adoption of sustainable mobility options. In Orvieto, on the other hand, a real-world test of the app was conducted, while the app was still on its Beta edition, actively involving citizens in tracking their routes, monitoring air quality, and exchanging tokens. Participants used the app to navigate specific areas and later redeem tokens for goods and services at local businesses. This hands-on engagement not only familiarized users with the DivAirCity platform but also demonstrated the value of tokenized rewards in promoting sustainable habits.

As the number of users evolves, cities are now considering expanding the marketplace with new types of items that also align with green mobility and education. Among the proposed additions are vouchers to use PV-powered chargers, which further ease the adoption of renewable energy solutions, and free access to online courses benefiting education and awareness on sustainability-related topics. These marketplace offerings ensure that every token spent contributes either to environmental preservation or to knowledge-sharing.

B. Educational Tool and Research Data Source

Beyond engaging citizens in sustainability efforts, the DivAirCity app can also serve as a valuable educational tool for students and a data source for sustainability research. By combining blockchain and cloud technologies and real-time environmental data collection, the app would offer students a good practical example of implementing emerging fields such as blockchain-based incentivization systems and smart city solutions. As a result, students would learn about decentralized data management, token economies and the importance of urban sustainability practices, through the app's practical use.

Moreover, the citizen-generated data, collected across the five pilot cities -Bucharest, Aarhus, Orvieto, Potsdam and Castellón- includes five different air quality indices, measured at various locations, along different user's traversed routes. This dataset, combined with information on routes or areas of interest and on behavioral changes, could provide a valuable resource for urban sustainability research. Researchers can analyze this data to identify air pollution patterns, assess the impact of behavioral interventions on urban emissions and explore the effectiveness of blockchain-based incentive models in promoting sustainable practices.

To summarize, this dual role of the app -as an educational tool and a research resource- not only helps students and researchers deepen their understanding of urban sustainability

and emerging technologies but also contributes to the creation of data-driven policies for smarter, greener cities.

C. Potential Enhancements

To further enhance public awareness and behavioral change, the DivAirCity app could integrate AI-driven features to allow for personalized insights, optimized incentives and enhanced environmental data analysis. An AI-powered air quality prediction system could analyze historical air pollution data, weather patterns and traffic conditions to forecast pollution levels in different urban areas. This would allow users to make informed route choices, while also providing city planners with predictive models for emission reduction strategies.

Additionally, machine learning algorithms could refine the token-based reward system, dynamically adjusting incentives, based on user behavior and engagement patterns. This would ensure that rewards are optimized to maximize participation, further reinforcing sustainable habits among users. Furthermore, AI could improve the detection of transportation modes, distinguishing between walking, cycling, public transport and private car use with greater accuracy. By leveraging sensor data from mobile devices, GPS patterns and even accelerometer readings, an AI-based model could automate transportation mode classification, ensuring that rewards are distributed fairly and more accurately.

By incorporating AI-driven environmental forecasting and adaptive incentivization, DivAirCity could further extend its role in encouraging eco-friendly behavior, while simultaneously generating valuable data for academic research and urban policy development.

VI. CONCLUSION

The DivAirCity app demonstrates the effective integration of blockchain, cloud infrastructure, and decentralized data management to promote citizen engagement and sustainable urban practices. By incentivizing eco-friendly behaviors such as walking, cycling and public transportation through transparent token rewards, the app fosters behavioral change while ensuring user privacy through encryption and GDPR compliance. Its modular architecture enables scalability and seamless replication across different cities, ensuring adaptability and maintainability to diverse urban environments. Additionally, DivAirCity serves as a valuable educational and research tool, providing real-time environmental data for analysis of behavioral patterns and pollution trends. Future enhancements—such as AI-driven features—will further improve user engagement and environmental impact. This paper presents a scalable, replicable, and effective model for fostering behavioral change, supporting educational initiatives, and driving urban sustainability in pursuit of climate-neutral cities.

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